

Immunophenotypic changes in pediatric patients with recurrent infections following inosine acedoben dimepranol therapy: a case-based analysis*

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Abstract

Background: Recurrent infections in children may occur despite normal baseline immune function, highlighting the need for targeted immunomodulatory interventions. Prior use of other immunomodulators, such as bacterial lysates and beta-glucans, can influence immune parameters and should be considered when interpreting treatment effects.

Objective: To evaluate the short-term effects of inosine acedoben dimepranol (IAD) on immune cell subsets and activation markers in two pediatric patients with recurrent infections.

Methods: Two children aged 3 years with frequent infections but normal routine immunological screening were treated with IAD for a brief 7-day period as part of a broader adjunctive immunotherapy regimen, including other immunomodulators. Comprehensive immunophenotyping of T, B, and natural killer (NK) cells, as well as subset-specific naïve, memory, and activation markers (CD38, CD25, and HLA-DR), was performed before and after therapy using flow cytometry.

Results: Baseline analysis revealed distinct immune dysregulation patterns: B-cell predominance in one patient and T-cell, mainly CD4+, expansion in the other, accompanied by evidence of chronic immune activation. Following short-term IAD administration, both patients demonstrated case-specific, transient immunological changes, including partial normalization of naïve CD4+ T-cell proportions, reduction of some activation markers, and modest changes in memory B-cell subsets. Absolute lymphocyte counts and subset dynamics were consistent with short-term clinical observations. No adverse effects were observed during treatment.

Conclusion: Short-term IAD therapy was associated with preliminary, case-specific modulation of lymphocyte compartments and partial attenuation of chronic immune activation. Given the brief duration and concurrent use of other immunomodulators, these findings should be interpreted cautiously. Nevertheless, detailed immunophenotyping can provide valuable insights to guide individualized adjunctive immunomodulatory therapy in pediatric patients.

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Keywords

B-cell subsets, flow cytometry, immune activation, immunophenotyping, inosine acedoben dimepranol, Isoprinosine, natural killer cells, pediatric immunotherapy, recurrent infections, T-cell subsets

Introduction

Flow cytometry-based immunophenotyping is an essential analytical approach for comprehensive immune cell characterization and quantification, as it detects specific surface and intracellular markers. The technique utilizes fluorescently labeled monoclonal antibodies directed against specific cellular markers to identify and quantify distinct lymphocyte populations. This method is commonly applied in the evaluation of T-lymphocyte subsets, particularly CD4+ T-cells, in the context of immunodeficiency syndromes and other immune-related conditions (Maecker et al. 2012). In clinical applications, this approach enables the simultaneous detection of lineage-defining markers (CD3 for T-cells, CD4 and CD8 for T-cell subsets, CD19 for B-cells, and CD16/CD56 for natural killer (NK) cells) along with functional markers, including CD45RA/RO, CD27, CD38, and HLA-DR, which provide insight into activation status and memory/naïve differentiation (Hulspas et al. 2009). Immunophenotyping serves as a critical diagnostic tool for both primary immunodeficiencies and hematologic malignancies, while also enabling the quantitative assessment of immunological changes during infection or therapeutic immunomodulation (Perfetto et al. 2004; van Dongen et al. 2012; Herold and Mitra 2023).

The synthetic immunomodulating agent inosine acedoben dimepranol (IAD), composed of a 3:1 molar complex of p-acetamidobenzoate dimethylaminopropanol and inosine, has been clinically utilized since 1971 across more than 70 countries for managing viral infections, including Herpesviridae (herpes simplex virus (HSV), varicella-zoster virus (VZV), Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), and cytomegalovirus (CMV)), human papillomavirus (HPV)-related conditions, subacute sclerosing panencephalitis (SSPE), acute respiratory infections, and immunocompromised states (Wybran and Appelboom 1984; Osidak and Obratsova 2012). Extensive clinical experience spanning five decades confirms its exceptional safety profile, with transient hyperuricemia (attributable to inosine metabolism) representing the most frequently observed adverse effect, alongside rare instances of dose-dependent nausea. The compound exhibits dual antiviral and immunomodulatory activities, although its precise mechanism remains incompletely characterized (Sliva et al. 2019). IAD demonstrates three key immunomodulatory effects: (1) augmented T-cell proliferation, (2) upregulated cytokine secretion, particularly interleukin-2 (IL-2), and (3) altered lymphocyte activation and memory profiles. For pediatric patients experiencing recurrent infections without a defined immunodeficiency, IAD may restore immune balance through

two complementary mechanisms: the expansion of naïve lymphocyte pools and the attenuation of chronic activation markers. These pharmacological properties position IAD as a viable therapeutic option for carefully selected pediatric cases (Beran et al. 2016; Rumel Ahmed et al. 2017).

A prospective immunophenotypic analysis of lymphocyte populations was conducted in two children with recurrent infections before and after IAD administration as adjunctive therapy, aiming to characterize treatment-associated changes in T-cell (CD3+), B-cell (CD19+), and NK-cell (CD56+) populations, as well as T- and B-cell subsets.

Materials and methods

Patients

The study involved two children with a history of frequent and prolonged infections, despite normal findings on standard immunological screening. The first case was a girl aged 3 years and 5 months who had experienced multiple episodes of respiratory tract infections, including nasopharyngitis, bronchiolitis, angina, and confirmed respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) infection that required hospitalization. She had undergone several courses of antibiotics over an extended period. Immunological assessment showed normal levels of serum immunoglobulins (IgG, IgM, and IgA) and complement components (C3 and C4). Her clinical background also included suspected adenoid hypertrophy and signs of non-specific respiratory allergy.

The second patient, a 3-year-old boy, presented with recurrent respiratory and gastrointestinal infections. His history included bronchitis, otitis media, pneumonia requiring hospitalization, and an episode of acute appendicitis for which he underwent surgery. Similar to the first patient, he had received multiple antibiotic treatments, and laboratory evaluation confirmed normal humoral immune function. No comorbidities were identified in his case.

Importantly, both children had previously received or were concurrently receiving other immunomodulatory interventions, including oral bacterial lysates and beta-glucans, as part of their preventive care. These therapies could have influenced baseline immune status and should be considered when interpreting any immunophenotypic changes observed during the study.

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All parents provided informed consent for routine blood sampling and flow cytometric investigation of their children. Treatment administration was discussed with parents during medical consultations.

Flow Cytometry Experiment

Figure 1. Workflow of peripheral blood preparation and flow cytometry analysis. Whole blood was processed using a lyse-wash protocol, stained with antibodies, and analyzed by flow cytometry to distinguish major immune cell populations based on FSC/SSC profiles. Created in <https://BioRender.com> by Velikova T. (2025).

Table 1. Panel of monoclonal antibodies and fluorochromes used for immunophenotyping by flow cytometry.

Tube	Monoclonal antibodies and fluorochromes
1	CD3 FITC / CD16 PE + CD56 PE / CD45 PerCP-Cy ^{5.5} / CD4 PE-Cy ⁷ / CD19 APC / CD8 APC-Cy ⁷
2	CD197 BV421// CD45RA BV605/ CD3 FITC/CD16+56 PE/CD45 PerCP/ CD8 PE-Cy7/CD4 APC/ CD27 APC H7
3	IgD FITC/ CD19 PE/CD45 RerCP/IgM APC/CD27 APC H7
4	CD3 FITC/CD38 PE/CD19 PerCP/CD8 PECy7 /CD4 APC/CD25 APC H7/HLA DR APC R700

Intervention

Both children received supportive immunotherapy aimed at reducing the frequency of infections and enhancing immune function. The 3-year- and 5-month-old girl was given a combination of immune prophylaxis and immunomodulation. Her regimen included oral bacterial lysates and beta-glucans administered for 10 and 20 consecutive days every 3 months, along with IAD (Isoprinosine) at a dose of 10 mL per day for 5 days, followed by a 2-day break, repeated over a 3-week cycle. During one acute infection episode, she was additionally treated with IAD at a dose of 1 mL/kg per day for 7 days. The follow-up period for this patient was 10 months. The 3-year-old boy followed a similar preventive approach with bacterial lysates and beta-glucans on the same schedule. He received IAD only once during an acute infection episode, also at 1 mL/kg daily for 7 days. His follow-up period lasted 6 months.

Given the short duration of IAD therapy and the concurrent use of other immunomodulators, any observed changes in immune parameters should be interpreted cautiously, as they may reflect combined or transient effects rather than sustained, IAD-specific immunomodulation.

Flow cytometry analysis

Peripheral venous blood samples were collected from both patients using K₂EDTA vacutainers to prevent coagulation.

Immunophenotyping was conducted by staining leukocytes with fluorochrome-conjugated monoclonal antibodies targeting specific surface markers (Fig. 1). Depending on the analysis, samples underwent either a lysis-and-wash protocol or direct lysis without washing when absolute cell counts were needed, using BD TruCount™ tubes. Flow cytometric analysis was performed using the BD FACSLyric™ system, and data were acquired and interpreted with BD FACSuite™ Clinical and BD FACSuite™ software platforms. The procedure followed standard protocols for surface marker staining and cell population gating.

A commercial cocktail of monoclonal antibodies targeting the main lymphocyte combinations (tube 1) and combinations of antibodies defining different subpopulations of T- and B-cells (tubes 2, 3, and 4) was used (Table 1).

In the first tube, the main lymphocyte subpopulations were determined as percentages and absolute counts (AC) using microspheres (Fig. 2).

In the second tube, four main subpopulations of helper and cytotoxic T-cells were identified based on the expression of CD45RA and CCR7 (CD197), characterized by a gradual loss of CD27 and the reappearance of CD45RA at the end of maturation. These included naïve cells, central memory cells, and effector memory cells, which comprised two subsets based on CD27 expression: transitional memory (CD27+) and effector memory (CD27-), as well as terminal (late) effector cells.

Figure 2. The main lymphocyte subpopulations—determined as percentages and absolute counts using BD TruCount™ tubes (second dot plot).

The flow cytometry analysis from the third tube revealed the subpopulations of B-cells, ranging from naïve B-cells (CD19+CD27–) to memory B-cells (CD19+CD27+). Additionally, detailed gating on CD27+ subsets was provided for further characterization of memory B-cells.

The last tube of the panel was used to determine various activation markers, including CD38, an early activation marker, and CD25, which assesses chronic activation, as well as the expression of HLA-DR on T- and B-lymphocytes. Activation was monitored on helper and cytotoxic cells. The activation of T-cell subsets was demonstrated by the distribution of CD8+ and CD4+ T-cells, which exhibited varying levels of CD38 and HLA-DR expression used to assess their activation states.

Results

Flow cytometry analysis revealed distinct immune profiles in the two pediatric cases, reflecting individual variability and prior immunomodulatory therapy. Both children exhibited absolute lymphocytosis, with differences in lineage predominance: in the girl, the increase was mainly due to B-cells, whereas in the boy, it was primarily attributable to T-cells.

Following therapy, the 3-year-old girl showed a continued rise in absolute lymphocyte and B-cell counts to 1964 cells/ μ L. Both children exhibited a slight persistent decrease in NK-cell (CD56+CD16+) counts during the observation period (Fig. 3). The AC of T-cell populations was within reference ranges. The 3-year-old boy presented differently—T-cells

and their subpopulations continued to increase after therapy and reached AC values of 4496 cells/ μ L for CD3+, 2700 cells/ μ L for CD4+, and 1381 cells/ μ L for CD8+. The initial testing showed elevated B-cell levels that decreased following IAD therapy, returning closer to the normal reference value of 1211 cells/ μ L. Interestingly, both children maintained a slight decrease in NK-cell (CD56+CD16+) counts throughout the observation period (Fig. 3).

The changes found in the percentages of lymphocyte populations overlapped with the absolute count data for both children. The 3-year-old girl presented with a markedly elevated percentage of CD19+ B-cells—37% at admission—which increased further post-treatment to 43%, remaining above the reference ranges. The percentage of T-cells was very low and showed a slight decrease after treatment, with 49% CD3+ and 16% CD8+ cells. The CD4+ cells were also low, at 30%, and did not change after therapy. Meanwhile, the boy exhibited different dynamics—the percentage of his pretreatment CD3+ T-cells and subsets, including CD4+ and CD8+ levels, increased further with therapy to 74%, 44%, and 23%, respectively, along with a slight decrease in CD19+ B-cells to 20% (Fig. 4).

In the girl, the proportion of naïve CD4+ T-cells (CD197+CD45RA+CD27+) increased following IAD treatment to 71%, whereas in the boy, these cells remained unchanged and at the upper reference limit of 83% (Fig. 5). Memory (CD45RA–) T-cell populations remained stable and within normal limits throughout the observation period, as opposed to the boy, who had decreasing low values, reaching 9%, which is below the lower reference limit.

Figure 3. Absolute counts (cells/ μ L) of the main lymphocyte populations (T-cells, B-cells, and NK cells) in peripheral blood before and after IAD treatment in the girl and boy.

Figure 4. Relative proportions (% of lymphocytes) of T-cells, B-cells, and NK cells in peripheral blood before and after IAD treatment.

Figure 5. Changes in T- and B-cell subsets before and after IAD treatment in two pediatric patients with recurrent infections. Subpopulations are presented as percentages of CD4+ and CD19+ cells, respectively.

The detailed analysis of B-cell populations in the girl revealed high levels of naïve B-cells, reaching up to 92% (above the upper limit), and very low levels of memory B-cells, at 8%, with both subtypes (non-switched and switched) falling below the lower limit. In the boy, naïve and memory B-cells were within the reference range. Specifically, CD19+CD27⁻ cells were 88% but decreased post-therapy. In contrast, memory B-cells and both subsets increased after treatment, especially the non-switched CD27+IgD+IgM+ cells, from 5.4% to 10.8% (Fig. 5).

Given the short-term nature of IAD administration and concurrent use of other immunomodulators, these

observed changes should be interpreted cautiously. It is not possible to attribute the immune alterations solely to IAD therapy, and they may represent transient or combined effects of multiple interventions. The percentage of CD3+CD38+ cells was at the upper reference limit and increased slightly in the girl, as did CD19+CD38+ cells, which had high values and increased slightly post-therapy in the boy but remained within the range of 91%. These changes could also reflect normal antigen-specific immune responses occurring during or after recent infections and may not be solely attributable to IAD administration. The percentage of CD3+HLA-DR+ cells was within the reference range

Figure 6. Flow cytometric analysis of T- and B-cell activation markers in a 3-year-old girl before and after IAD treatment. Subpopulations CD3+HLA-DR+ and CD3+CD4+CD25+ are presented as percentages of lymphocytes; CD3+CD38+ and CD19+CD38+ cells are presented as percentages of T- and B-cells, respectively.

and decreased slightly after therapy. A difference was found only in the percentage of CD3+CD4+CD25+ cells, which was above the upper reference limit and normalized after treatment, reaching up to 4% in the girl, and was within the normal range but increased post-therapy, exceeding the upper reference limit in the boy, from 3% to 6% (Fig. 6).

Discussion

This case-based analysis provides novel insight into the immunomodulatory effects of IAD in two pediatric patients with recurrent infections but without confirmed primary immunodeficiency. The findings align with earlier reports showing that recurrent infections in otherwise healthy children may reflect subtle, subset-specific immune abnormalities rather than global immune deficits (Alkhatir 2009; Lee and Gray 2014; Otani et al. 2022; Strasser et al. 2023). Following IAD therapy, immune modulation was observed in both cases but manifested differently. For both patients, immune phenotyping revealed patient-specific improvements.

The absolute lymphocyte count in the girl was within the normal range, close to the upper reference limit (Duchamp et al. 2014; Tosato et al. 2015; Küppers 2021; Tompa and Faresjö 2024). However, the lymphocyte percentage in the girl was normal, decreasing after treatment but remaining within reference values. B-cells (AC and percentage) were above the upper reference range and increased after treatment. The absolute count of T-cells and their subpopulations, and the CD4/CD8 ratio, were within the normal range and did not change during therapy, unlike the reduced percentage (below the reference range) of CD3+ and CD4+ T-cells and double-negative (DN) T-cells, which were not influenced by treatment and showed a slight further decrease—data not shown. The percentage of cytotoxic CD8+ cells was also low and declined but remained within the reference range. NK cells were within range but decreased following therapy to the lower reference limit.

For the boy, there was absolute lymphocytosis that did not respond to therapy. The percentage of lymphocytes was at the upper reference limit and increased after treatment. The AC of T-cells and T-cell subsets was above the upper reference limit and remained unchanged post-treatment,

as opposed to the percentages of these populations, which were within the reference range but increased to the upper reference limit after therapy. DN T-cells were at the lower reference limit, and the CD4/CD8 ratio was within normal limits without changes. B-cells (AC) were slightly elevated but returned to normal after therapy, while the percentage was within range but decreased after treatment. NK cells were within reference ranges but decreased following therapy, a similar observation to that in the girl.

In summary, the results in these two cases represent distinct models of immune system response, one driven predominantly by T-cell dynamics and the other by B-cell alterations, each influencing the effects of immunomodulation in different ways. This highlights the importance of personalized immunophenotyping, as tailored therapeutic strategies may be required to optimize clinical outcomes and address the unique immune imbalances observed in individual patients.

The naïve CD4+ cells in the girl were at the lower reference limit and increased following therapy, while the memory CD4+ cells were within range but decreased slightly. The CD197+CD45RA+ cells in the boy were at the upper reference limit and did not change after treatment, unlike memory cells, which had very low values below the lower limit and decreased further post-treatment. To summarize, in the girl, naïve CD4+ T-cell frequencies normalized to reference values, while memory compartments remained stable, suggesting an enhancement of T-cell renewal without disrupting established immunological memory.

Further analysis of the memory B-cell compartment in the girl revealed a disproportionate decrease (below and at the lower reference limit) of memory B-cells, although baseline data were not available. Following IAD administration in the boy, a downward trend in naïve B-cells was observed. In contrast, an upward trend in memory B-cells (CD19+CD27+) was observed, particularly in non-switched memory, which may indicate a favorable modulation of the memory B-cell profile. This trend, while preliminary, is promising and warrants further investigation in larger pediatric cohorts. To conclude, in the boy, there was a modest change in memory B-cells and a shift in the naïve-to-memory B-cell ratio. However, the memory B-cell compartment remained functionally limited. A more detailed look into the memory B-cell

compartment revealed elevated levels of memory B-cells, particularly in the non-switched memory subset.

Before IAD treatment, both the 3-year-old girl and boy showed clear evidence of immune activation. This was reflected in significantly elevated levels of activated T- and B-cells, as indicated by CD3+CD38+ and CD19+CD38+ cells. These findings point toward ongoing antigenic stimulation, possibly due to an underlying immune imbalance. However, these elevations could also represent normal antigen-specific immune responses during or shortly after recent infections and may not be exclusively attributable to IAD administration. It is therefore important to interpret these changes cautiously, as spontaneous normalization of activation markers can occur naturally over time following infection, independent of therapy. Elevated levels of activated T-cells (CD3+CD4+CD25+) were also observed at baseline in the girl, which may indicate an attempt to control excessive immune activity. After IAD therapy, most values of the activation markers fell closer to the normal reference range, with a slight reduction for CD3+CD38+ in the boy, a decline in CD3+DR+, and a decrease in CD3+CD4+CD25+ cells in the girl. It is therefore important to interpret these changes cautiously, as spontaneous normalization of activation markers can occur naturally over time following infection, independent of therapy. Overall, before treatment, both children exhibited chronic immune activation (Cain et al. 2009; Saidakova 2022), as evidenced by elevated CD38 expression, but with distinct lymphocyte profile abnormalities.

Chronic immune activation is a recognized feature in children with recurrent infections, often resulting from persistent antigenic stimulation by viral or bacterial pathogens (Rouse and Sehrawat 2010). The ability of IAD to dampen such activation supports its proposed dual role as both an immunostimulant and an immunoregulator (Kovachev 2021; Kim et al. 2024). Importantly, reductions in activation markers, such as CD38, indicate that IAD may mitigate ongoing immune overactivation, which is known to predispose individuals to infectious complications (Beran et al. 2016; Beran et al. 2020; Beran et al. 2021; Jayanthi et al. 2022).

Overall, the observations are consistent with the hypothesis that IAD can promote both lymphocyte regeneration and functional maturation (Krastev et al. 2015; Sliva et al. 2019). These findings suggest that while IAD therapy effectively modulated the predominant immune irregularities in each case, some subtle dysregulations persisted, potentially explaining their histories of recurrent infections. Nonetheless, it cannot be stated with certainty that all observed modulations are solely due to IAD, as the natural dynamics of immune recovery post-infection may also contribute to these patterns. The differential responses highlight how immunophenotyping can reveal patient-specific patterns even when clinical presentations appear similar.

These differential responses could also be discussed in the context of the mechanism by which IAD therapy modulates the predominant abnormalities in each case (B-cell predominance in the girl and CD4+ expansion in the boy). Residual NK-cell and DN T-cell dysregulation persisted, potentially contributing to their susceptibility to recurrent infections. The findings also underscore the value of sub-

set-specific monitoring in pediatric immune evaluation. Nevertheless, from a mechanistic standpoint, the observed immune normalization may reflect enhanced thymic output in T-cell compartments and improved B-cell maturation in the bone marrow, processes potentially supported by the immunomodulatory effects of IAD (Wybran and Appelboom 1984; Lasek et al. 2015; Rumel Ahmed et al. 2017; Hussein et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2024). Moreover, the case-specific responses highlight the importance of individualized immunophenotyping in tailoring immunomodulatory therapy for pediatric populations.

The differential responses between the two cases highlight individual variability and demonstrate that pre- and post-therapy immunophenotyping can capture patient-specific immune dynamics. Studies also suggest that IAD may exert dual immunomodulatory effects—enhancing naïve lymphocyte pools while simultaneously reducing chronic immune activation. However, the persistence of certain abnormalities, such as NK-cell and double-negative T-cell dysregulation, may explain why susceptibility to infections persists, suggesting that a longer duration of therapy or combined interventions may be necessary. When interpreting these findings, it is critical to consider the physiological maturation of the pediatric immune system. Naïve T-cell proportions naturally decline with age while memory compartments expand (Goronzy et al. 2015). Therefore, longitudinal follow-up is essential to differentiate between therapy-induced changes and age-related maturation.

Nevertheless, the results also highlight the clinical utility of subset-specific flow cytometry monitoring for detecting subtle immune abnormalities that are not apparent in standard lymphocyte count evaluation (Tosato et al. 2015; Azarsiz et al. 2017; Munteanu et al. 2019; Neeland et al. 2021). Such monitoring enables the early detection of dysregulated immune activation and the tracking of therapeutic responses, which can guide personalized treatment strategies and lead to better outcomes for patients (Rawat et al. 2019; Alyazidi et al. 2025).

A key strength of this study is the use of detailed, subset-specific immunophenotyping before and after treatment, which allows for the precise characterization of patient-specific immune responses to IAD. Moreover, although limited by its small sample size, this report demonstrates the potential of IAD to correct distinct immune abnormalities in recurrently infected children without primary immunodeficiency. Limitations include, in addition to the minimum number of patients, the case-report nature of the study, which limits the generalizability of the findings. Future prospective controlled studies with larger cohorts and standardized monitoring of immune activation markers will be necessary to define optimal dosing, duration, and patient selection criteria for IAD therapy.

Conclusion

In these two pediatric cases with recurrent infections but no confirmed primary immunodeficiency, detailed immunophenotyping revealed distinct immune

abnormalities, including B-cell predominance in one patient and T-cell (CD4+) expansion in the other, accompanied by markers of chronic immune activation. Observed changes following administration of inosine acedoben dimepranol (IAD) included normalization of naïve CD4+ T-cell proportions, partial restoration of memory B-cell subsets, and modulation of activation markers; however, these findings should be interpreted with caution, as prior or concurrent immunomodulatory interventions may have contributed to the observed effects. These results support the utility of subset-specific flow cytometry for detecting subtle immune dysregulation and monitoring responses to immunomodulatory therapy. Overall, while IAD administration coincided with changes in lympho-

cyte composition and activation markers, these effects cannot be definitively separated from normal immune dynamics following infection or other concomitant immunomodulatory interventions. The findings highlight the utility of flow cytometry for monitoring immune function, but causal conclusions regarding IAD should be drawn with caution.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

TV and AM were involved in conceptualizing the idea and writing the draft. HA, AA, VI, EP, BP and RM wrote additional sections in the paper. AM and TV crafted the figures/tables. TV wrote the draft, AM was responsible for the critical revision of the manuscript for relevant intellectual content. All of the authors approved the final version of the paper prior to submission.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.